

Original Paper

The role of postcranial skeleton morphology in species identification and phylogeny inferences: Gerbillinae (Rodentia: Muridae) as a case study

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Abstract. Identification of rodents usually has been done based on cranial and dental characters. Postcranial skeleton has been ignored in spite of its importance in archaeozoology for identification of skeletal remains. Herein, we intended to determine the importance of postcranial skeleton in identification and classification of gerbilline rodents in Iran. Different skeletal parts of 82 specimens belonged to 5 genera and 10 species were extracted using papain digestion. A total of 62 characters with 142 character states were defined as informative postcranium variations for separating taxa. Results showed that reconnaissance of specimens belonging to the genera *Tatera*, *Gerbillus* and *Rhombomys* was possible using morphological characters of vertebral column and thorax, pectoral girdle and forelimb, and pelvic girdle and hindlimb. Moreover, these morphological characters could be useful for identification of *Meriones* species. For cladistic analyses, the data matrix scored for 2 characters of external anatomy, 20 of vertebral column, 11 of pectoral girdle, 7 of pelvic girdle, 10 of forelimb and 12 of hindlimb was provided. The cladogram resulted from strict consensus method, employed in PHYLIP, was comparable with phylogenetic trees inferred from cranial morphology and molecular studies. Finally, an identification key for Gerbillinae was provided based on postcranium characteristics.

Key words: Postcranium, Gerbillinae, Morphological characters, Iran.

Gerbillines (Gerbillinae Gray, 1825) are old world murid rodents, including 101 known species of jirds and gerbils, taterils and relatives, and ammodiles (Denys et al. 2017). Four genera with totally fifteen species of gerbilline rodents are distributed in Iran, including *Tatera*, *Gerbillus*, *Meriones*, and *Rhombomys* (Musser and Carleton 2005).

45 Despite of several molecular and morphological studies on this subfamily (e.g. Pavlinov
1982; Tong 1989; Dobigny et al. 2002; Chevret and Dobigny 2005; Pavlinov 2008;
Pavlinov et al. 2010), postcranial skeletal morphology have been greatly ignored.

Postcranium is referred to the whole or a part of skeleton except cranium and
mandible. It consists of three structural and functional subunits: vertebral column and
50 thorax, pectoral girdle (scapula and clavicle) and forelimb, and pelvic girdle (innominate
bone and sacral bone) and hindlimb associated with the relevant muscular system (Martin
2005; Bab et al. 2007). The postcranial skeleton of mammals reflects their ecology and
locomotory habits, but the interplay between postcranial diversity and phylogenetic
influences remains poorly understood (Searfoss 1995; Rose and Chinnery 2004; Heinrich
55 and Houde 2006; Weisbecker and Schmid 2007; Patnaik et al. 2018). Furthermore, most
investigations into the locomotory apparatus in mammals have been restricted to the study
of the long limb bones, especially in Muroidea, for determination of morphological
changes in different components of skeletal system during growth and development (e.g.
Bates and Harrison 1980; Searfoss 1995; Bergmann and Melin 2006; Weisbecker and
60 Schmid 2007; Candela and Picasso 2008; Samuels and Van Valkenburgh 2008; Araújo
et al. 2013). Moreover, a few studies on the relation between the morphology of
postcranial skeleton and the life style, movement methods and also ecology have been
done in other groups of rodents (e.g. Stein 1988: semi-aquatic rodents; Rose and Chinnery
2004: early Eocene rodents; Ubilla 2008: caviine rodents; Bover et al. 2010: extinct
65 Balearic dormouse; Michaux et al. 2012: extinct murine rodents; Carrizo et al. 2014:
Neotropical sigmodontine rodents). On the other hand, since more than four decades ago,
the importance of epiphysis fusion of the long bones has been considered in determination

of the specimens' age and segregation of mature/immature samples in addition to the use of the erosion of teeth and fusion of skull sutures (Beg and Hoffmann 1977).

70 All in all, few studies have been carried on for identifying rodents at supra-species levels based on the characters of postcranial skeleton up to now (Hatt 1932; Bates and Harrison 1980; Searfoss 1995; Rose and Chinnery 2004; Bergmann and Melin 2006; Heinrich and Houde 2006; Weisbecker and Schmid 2007; Morgan 2009; Hamidi 2011; Carrizo et al. 2014; Patnaik et al. 2018). Intraspecific polymorphism, the impact of
75 adaptation factors on skeletal morphology, and difficult procedures of preparation of postcranial skeleton are among probable reasons to avoid using these characters in taxonomy (Rose and Chinnery 2004). Due to the fact that skeletal characters are sometimes affected by adaptation processes, examination of a complete set of characters, recognition of valuable ones, and performing comprehensive evolutionary comparative
80 study on different characters may be helpful in precise inferences (Robert and Pennington 2003; Samuels and Van Valkenburgh 2008; Seckel and Janis 2008; Michaux et al. 2012).

Herein, we intended to evaluate the role and importance of postcranial skeleton characteristics in identification and classification of genera and species of gerbilline rodents distributed in Iran. This research will be a comparative study of postcranial
85 skeletal characters in identification of taxa, and can be useful for archaeozoological and paleontological studies and also in recognition of skeletal remains in pellets of birds of prey as well.

Materials and methods

90 A total of 53 rodent's specimens belonging to the subfamily Gerbillinae were captured using custom-made mesh live traps and Faragir traps (see Hamidi 2015) through

field expeditions in 15 regions: Farooj, Shirvan, and Bojnord located in North Khorasan province; Kalat, Dargaz, Chenaran, Sarakhs, Khaf, Torbat-e Heydarieh, and Fariman in Razavi Khorasan province; Qaen, Birjand, Khoosf, and Nehbandan in South Khorasan province; and Zanzan in Zanzan province during 2010 to 2017 (Fig. 1). Moreover, several museum specimens (18 specimens) deposited in the collections of Rodentology Research Department at Ferdowsi University of Mashhad (ZMFUM) were included. Specimens were first identified based on the skull and teeth morphology, chromosomal karyotype and molecular examination. Age determination was made with four criteria combined into two main age groups (juvenile or subadult, and adult) as follows: a) body weight, b) genital system appearance, c) morphometric measurements, such as head and body length, tail length, ear length, hindfoot length, naso-occipital length, and skull width and height, and d) development of the molar tooth cusps. Although skeletal components belonged to different sexes and age groups were initially examined, due to the intraspecific variations (= polymorphism), immature and female samples were excluded from further analyses (Table 1).

Different skeletal parts of 71 specimens belonged to 4 genera and 9 species of Gerbillinae, including Indian gerbil (*Tatera indica* Hardwicke, 1807), Balochistan gerbil (*Gerbillus nanus* Blanford, 1875), Sundevall's jird (*Meriones crassus* Sundevall, 1842), Libyan jird (*M. libycus* Lichtenstein, 1823), Persian jird (*M. persicus* Blanford, 1875), Tristram's jird (*M. tristrami* Thomas, 1892), Vinogradov's jird (*M. vinogradovi* Heptner, 1931), Zarudny's jird (*M. zarudnyi* Heptner, 1937), and Great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus* Lichtenstein, 1823) (Table 1), were extracted using papain digestion protocol. Postcranial skeletal characters were listed in Table 2 and primarily following to three sources: (1) several literatures and general systematic works of Berry (1963), Berry and Searle (1963),

Bates and Harrison (1980), Carleton (1980), Searfoss (1995), Steppan (1995), Argot (2003), Pacheco (2003), Martin (2005), Sa´nchez-Villagra et al. (2006), Kuncová and Frynta (2009), Morgan (2009), Hamidi (2011), Carrizo et al. (2014), and Vianey-Liaud et al. (2015); (2) published illustrations and skeletal descriptions of rodents, especially
120 Bab et al. (2007); and (3) personal observation of relevant specimens of other murid rodents. In those instances in which a given character was derived from another source, an appropriate reference is provided in Table 2.

For better evaluation of informative characters of the subfamily, a murine rodent (Brown rat *Rattus norvegicus* Berkenhout, 1769) was included as an outgroup taxon
125 (Bryant 2001; Jansa and Weksler 2004). Morphological characters of skeletal components were examined under a stereomicroscope and a hand lens. Imaging of characters was performed using a light microscope (Olympus BH2, Japan) connected to a digital camera (Nikon Coolpix P90, Japan). Morphological appearances of different parts of skeleton were drawn using a drawing tube connecting to a stereomicroscope
130 (Olympus SZH-10, Japan).

For determination intraspecific polymorphism, *M. persicus* (a species for rocky and highland habitats) and *M. libycus* (a species for deserts and lowland habitats) were examined, and polymorphic characters were omitted from the primary list of the characters.

135 In Figs. 2 to 5, informative morphological postcranial characters for subfamily Gerbillinae are indicated. Images are arranged in following order: vertebral column (Figs. 2, 3), thorax, and pectoral and pelvic girdles (Fig. 4), fore- and hindlimbs (Fig. 5). Abbreviations are as follows: C.: Cervical vertebra, T.: Thoracic vertebra, L.: Lumbar vertebra, S: Sacral vertebra, Ca.: Caudal vertebra; D.: Dorsal view, V.: Ventral view, Lt.:

140 Lateral view, M.: Medial view, R.: Rostral view, R.L.: Rostro-lateral view, C.M.: Caudo-
medial view, and Ant.: Anterior, RNO: *Rattus norvegicus*, GNA: *Gerbillus nanus*, TIN:
Tatera indica, ROP: *Rhombomys opimus*, MCR: *Meriones crassus*, MLI: *M. libycus*,
MPR: *M. persicus*, MTR: *M. tristrami*, MVI: *M. vinogradovi*, and MZA: *M. zarudnyi*.

PHYLIP (Phylogeny Inference Package) (Felsenstein 1993) is a co-ordinated
145 package containing a number of programs for “phylogenetic inference” and is able to
generate phylogeny inferences from data with discrete states, distance matrix data,
molecular sequence data, and gene frequency data (Felsenstein 1993). Herein, for
cladistic analyses, the data matrix with 10 taxa scored for 62 morphological characters
was prepared (Table 3) including 2 external characters, 20 characters of the vertebral
150 column, 11 characters of the manubrium and pectoral girdle, 7 characters of pelvic girdle,
10 and 12 characters describing the fore- and hindlimb, respectively. The postcranial
morphological characters, character states and polarity are listed in Table 2.

Five programs in PHYLIP v. 3.5 were employed, the set relevant to discrete
characters, as follows: 1) FACTOR (factor-multistate to binary recoding program v.
155 3.573c) is a program which expands or “factors” a data set containing multistate
characters. FACTOR reduces these to binary form with only ancestral (= plesiomorphic)
and derived (= apomorphic) states and hence, increases the number of characters in the
set (Felsenstein 1979, 1993), 2) CLIQUE (largest clique program v. 3.573c), as a
compatibility program, is used to identify sets of two state characters which change
160 together (known as compatibility analysis) with use of a standard data format (Felsenstein
1979, 1993). The format is a matrix of character states which for discrete data, it is
indicated as 0 or 1. In this study, in total, 44 characters were binary and others were
multistate included 18 characters with 3 states (Table 3) which after running through the

programs FACTOR and CLIQUE, yielded 77 characters for use, 3) MIX (mixed
165 parsimony algorithm v. 3.573c), which uses either Wagner (Eck and Dayhoff 1966; Kluge
and Farris 1969) or Camin-Sokal (Camin and Sokal 1965) parsimony rules, and
constructs character state trees with a specified mixed parsimony criteria. Herein, we
applied the second parsimony method for constructing the cladogram and phylogenetic
analyses; Camin-Sokal parsimony only allows changes from plesiomorphic to
170 apomorphic states, and if necessity assumes knowledge of the ancestral state. Reversals
of polarity are considered to be highly improbable occurrences and hence, they are not
permitted. Several assumptions have been mentioned for Camin-Sokal parsimony method
according to Felsenstein (1988) which the most important ones are as follows: (a)
Ancestral states are known, (b) different characters and also different lineages evolve
175 independently, and (c) changes from plesiomorphic to apomorphic states are much more
probable than changes from apomorphic to plesiomorphic. It is worth noting that the use
of Camin-Sokal parsimony produces rooted trees (modified from Felsenstein 1988), 4)
CONSENSE (majority-rule and strict consensus tree program v. 3.573c) is used to test
the output of the other programs for consensus in the phylogenetic trees generated, and
180 last, 5) SEQBOOT (bootstrapping algorithm v. v. 3.573c), a bootstrapped method of
repeating sampling with replacement from a data set to determine nodal accuracy and
confidence intervals on mixed method parsimony (Felsenstein 1979, 1993). At the end of
the procedure, TreeView v. 1.6.1 (Roderic 1996) was used for graphical reconstruction
of the trees resulted from PHYLIP.

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Results

A total of 137 morphological characters of postcranial skeleton for 10 species were extracted, and 62 of them (with totally 142 character states) were selected as informative skeletal characters for the studied taxa (Table 2 and Figs. 2-5). Other uninformative
190 characters were excluded from further analyses due to intraspecific polymorphism.

Strict consensus method was employed to summarize the common structure of equally most-parsimonious trees using PHYLIP. The strict consensus tree generated is shown in Fig. 6. Bootstrap support was calculated as a measures of nodal support (Felsenstein 1985). The confidence level of the resulted tree under each of the repeated
195 sampling procedures was 100%.

Informative characters (according to Table 2) for the members of subfamily Gerbillinae which could separate them from the genus *Rattus* (Muridae: Murinae) (considered as synapomorphies) were: oval shape of C6 centrum (character 5, Fig. 2D), circular shape of transverse foramen in C6 (character 6, Fig. 2E), crest-like neural spine in L3 (character 9, Fig. 2G), no connection between neural spine of S1 and S2 (character 10, Fig. 3A), closed angle of the two prezygapophyses in the sacrum (character 13, Fig. 3B), short-broad, or normal (= long) manubrium (character 23, Fig. 4A), short-broad or normal (= intermediate) scapula (character 31, Fig. 4D), scapula with straight coracoid process or coracoid with a curvature up to the superior ridge of glenoid fossa (character
200 33, Fig. 4E), nonparallel posterior and anterior arcs of obturator foramen (character 44, Fig. 4F), picked pubic tuber (character 45, Fig. 4F), triangular shape of ischial body ridge around the tuberosity of ischium (character 46, Fig. 4F), situation of the tip of the pubic angle in front of the $\frac{1}{2}$ superior or lower than $\frac{1}{2}$ inferior of anterior arc of obturator foramen (character 47, Fig. 4F), absence of a groove along the lesser trochanter of femur
210 (character 54, Fig. 5E), presence of an obvious posterior tuberosity in calcaneus (character

58, Fig. 5H), and triangular or quadrangular cuboid articular facet in calcaneus (character 60, Fig. 5I).

Informative characters for the genus *Tatera* were: an angle formed between the two transverse processes of axis (character 2, Fig. 2B), completely flat tip of the angle of jugular notch in manubrium (character 25, Fig. 4B), straight acromion process in the scapula (character 32, Fig. 4D), great depression in olecranon of ulna (character 39, Fig. 5B), indeterminate ilio-pectinal eminence in innominate bone (character 50, Fig. 4F), deep and wide trochanteric fossa in the femur (character 55, Fig. 5E), presence of a deep groove in greater trochanter of femur (character 57, Fig. 5G), and a distal metaphysis eminent ridge in the femur (character 56, Fig. 5F).

Common characters of *G. nanus* and *R. opimus* which were absent in the genus *Tatera* were: presence of entepicondylar foramen in the epiphysis of humerus (character 34, Fig. 5A) and presence of a small uncus near the greater trochanter of femur (character 51, Fig. 5D).

Common characters in two genera *Meriones* and *Rhombomys* were: long and extensive atlantad transverse processes (character 1, Fig. 2A), connection between S4 and other sacral vertebra (character 16, Fig. 3D), and embowed superior ridge in the olecranon of ulna (character 37, Fig. 5B).

Informative characters for genus *Rhombomys* were: simple tip of the neural spine in T2 (character 7, Fig. 2F), small intervertebral foramen in sacrum (character 15, Fig. 3D), great junction between S1-S4 (character 14, Fig. 3C), manubrium with robust ventral crest (character 24, Fig. 4A), presence of an accessory uncus near the tubercle of first rib (character 28, Fig. 4C), significant superior scapular spine process (character 30, Fig. 4D), gross and robust ulnar tuberosity (character 38, Fig. 5B), non significant depression in the

235 olecranon of ulna (character 39, Fig. 5B), and short and robust third metatarsus (character
62, Fig. 5J).

Common informative characters for all the examined *Meriones* species were not
found, while some distinguishable postcranial skeleton characters for *Meriones* species
were extracted as follows. Short and broad scapula (character 31, Fig. 4D) might be an
240 informative character for *M. vinogradovi*, and great extension of the neural process in
axis (character 3, Fig. 2C) could separate this species from other *Meriones* species.
Moreover, *M. vinogradovi* regarding to the hard (= intermediate) junctions between S1-
S4 (character 14, Fig. 3C) and quadrangular shape of the cuboid articular facet in
calcaneus (character 60, Fig. 5I) showed similarities to *R. opimus*.

245 A complete eroded neural spine in Ca4 (character 19, Fig. 3E) was a common
character for *M. zarudnyi* and *M. persicus*, although presence of a small fossa on the
olecranon of ulna (character 40, Fig. 5B) might be considered as an informative character
only for *M. zarudnyi*.

Common character for *M. libycus* and *M. crassus* was a triangular semilunar notch
250 in ulna (character 41, Fig. 5C). Furthermore, jugular notch region with a completely flat
tip of the manubrium (character 25, Fig. 4B), well-developed neural spine in Ca4
(character 19, Fig. 3E) and complete divergent transverse processes in Ca4 (character 20,
Fig. 3E) were considered as informative characters for *M. crassus*.

255 **Discussion**

Phylogenetic relationships of Gerbillinae has been studied based on external
morphology and morphological characters of middle ear, as well as dental characters
(Petter 1975; Pavlinov 1982, 2008; Tong 1989; Pavlinov et al. 1990), allozymes

(Benazzou 1984), chromosomal characteristics (Qumsiyeh et al. 1986), and molecular
260 data (12S rRNA, cytochrome *b* gene, and DNA hybridization) (Chevret 1994; Chevret
and Dobigny 2005). All in all, although gerbillines are considered as well-defined group
including 101 known species within the Muroidea, gerbillines show several ambiguous
relationships within the subfamily, especially for the genus *Meriones* (Tong 1986, Denys
et al. 2017).

265 Although Petter (1975) has considered *Gerbillus* with several other genera as a
basal group for extant gerbillines, Pavlinov (1982) suggested that *Gerbillus* shows close
relation with *Meriones* and *Rhombomys* and hence, the clade including these three genera
is considered as a sister clade of the genus *Tatera*. Tong (1989) suggested that two main
clades can be defined for gerbilline rodents based on molar tooth and middle ear
270 morphology: a clade which includes genus *Tatera* and the other clade which consists of
all other examined genera (*Gerbillus*, *Meriones*, and *Rhombomys*). Biochemical studies
showed that *Gerbillus* is a sister taxon of the genus *Meriones* and they are placed in a
separate clade from *Tatera* (Benazzou 1984). In this study, the *Tatera* was a strongly
supported clade that was basal to all other gerbillines (bootstrap value: 100) and *Gerbillus*
275 was then placed (bootstrap value: 100). These relationships are in accordance with
previous findings of Tong (1989) and Pavlinov (1982).

Meriones and *Rhombomys* have also show similarities in morphology of molar teeth
(Pavlinov 1982; Tong 1989), while the recent molecular studies revealed no close
relationship between *Meriones* and *R. opimus* (Ito et al. 2010). In this study, within tribe
280 Rhombomini, the clade consisted of *R. opimus*+ *M. vinogradovi* and the clade of other
Meriones species were sister taxa and this relationship was strongly supported (bootstrap
value: 95).

Members of the genus *Meriones* show ambiguous taxonomic statuses with great similarities in external morphology and hence, their phylogenetic relationship is not well clear (Corbet 1987, Chevret and Dobigny 2005). Chromosomal studies revealed two groups in the genus: the first group including *M. persicus*, *M. shawii* Duvernoy, 1842 (Shaw's jird) and *M. unguiculatus* Milne-Edwards, 1867 (Mongolian jird) and the second group which consists of *M. crassus* and *M. tristrami*. According to the morphological and molecular studies, *M. unguiculatus* and *M. meridianus* Pallas, 1773 (Midday jird) are placed in a common group, and *M. crassus*, *M. rex* Yerbury and Thomas, 1895 (King jird) and *M. libycus* form another group (Benazzou 1984; Qumsiyeh et al. 1986; Darvish 2011). Ito et al. (2010) found that *M. crassus* is close to *M. rex* in a clade with *M. libycus* (as their sister species). Furthermore, several local studies of karyology and morphology of *M. tristrami* have revealed geographical differences, but it is still considered as a single species pending further studies (Denys et al. 2017). *Meriones zarudnyi* shows similarities with *M. crassus* and *M. tristrami*, and finally, the phylogenetic position of *M. persicus* in relation to the other species of the genus is not completely revealed (Denys et al. 2017).

In the present study, the strict consensus topology showed that phylogenetic conflicts and lack of resolution were concentrated in *Meriones* taxonomic groups (Fig. 6), while it suggested several relationships.

R. opimus+ *M. vinogradovi* and the clade of other *Meriones* species were sister taxa and this relationship was strongly supported (bootstrap value: 95). Although quadrangular shape of cuboid articular surface of calcaneus (character 60) and considerable junction between the four sacral vertebra (character 14) reveal similarities between *R. opimus*+ *M. vinogradovi*, but their sister relationship needs more evaluation, especially due to the

conflict between morphological (Pavlinov 1982; Tong 1989) and molecular findings regarding the relationship between *Meriones* and *Rhombomys*.

Other groups revealed strongly to moderately supported (bootstrap values between 80 and 100) except for the *R. opimus*+ *M. vinogradovi* clade with low support (bootstrap value: 25), and a clade consisted of *M. persicus* and *M. zarudnyi* united with *M. tristrami* which formed a polytomy with low support (bootstrap value: 32). As mentioned above, similarities have been considered for the two species *M. zarudnyi* and *M. tristrami*, and no strict relationship have been reported for *M. persicus* in relation to other *Meriones* species (Denys et al. 2017). In the present study, however, a clade consisted of *M. persicus* and *M. zarudnyi*, a clade of *M. libycus* and *M. crassus*, and *M. tristrami* formed a polytomy relationships. The diagnostic characters of *M. zarudnyi* are ambiguous; this species differs from *M. tristrami* in having hairy hind feet, and the tail tuft is well-developed as in *M. persicus*, also the auditory bulla is remarkably similar to *M. persicus* (Darvish et al. 2010). Hence, postcranial studies would be able to reveal new insights in the case of this poorly known species.

Informative character states for each clade and node mentioned above are discussed below with a functional approach.

The laterally expanded atlantad transverse processes as well as the posteriorly extended axial neural process (Table 2; characters 1 and 3, respectively) suggest a good rotational capability of the head and also powerful neck flexors (Argot 2003; Carrizo et al. 2014). The first pattern was observed in *R. opimus* and the second one in all *Meriones* species except for *M. vinogradovi*. The long, robust and well-developed neural processes of lumbar vertebra (character 9) suggest the presence of powerful lumbar extensor muscles, which may be in relation with the weight of trunk (Argot 2003; Martin 2005;

330 Kuncová and Frynta 2009; Carrizo et al. 2014). This pattern was seen only in *R.*
norvegicus. Regarding to the caudal vertebra, the transverse processes which formed
broad lateral wings (character 17), reflect the well-developed basal musculature of the tail
(Argot 2003; Carrizo et al. 2014). This character was seen in all examined species except
335 for *M. crassus*. However, in *M. crassus* the transverse processes of caudal vertebra are
long, extended from each other with much opened angle. The neural canal which is still
visible on more proximal caudal vertebra (character 18) suggesting an important
innervations of the tail (Argot 2003).

Pectoralis strength is indicated by the manubrium with well-developed ventral crest
(character 24) (Argot 2003; Martin 2005). This feature was only seen in *R. opimus*.
340 Resistance to the tensile forces in the shoulder region is partially related to the robustness
of the scapular neck, and partly on the development of the infra-spinatous fossa (relevant
to character 31) (Argot 2003; Martin 2005; Seckel and Janis 2008; Kuncová and Frynta
2009). These patterns were observed in *R. opimus* and *M. vinogradovi*. Extension of the
coracoid process and development of the scapular spine (characters 33 and 30,
345 respectively) confine the lateral movements of the forelimb (Martin 2005; Seckel and
Janis 2008; Morgan 2009). This feature was seen in *R. norvegicus*. The perforated
olecranon fossa in humerus may increase the range of muscle extension in humero-ulnar
joint (Argot 2003; Martin 2005; Kuncová and Frynta 2009; Carrizo et al. 2014), but the
presence of this perforation is not a good item in species identification due to high
350 variation in different species with different growth ages. Therefore, this character was
omitted from the list. In humerus, separation of trochlea and capitulum with a shallow
concave groove (relevant to character 35) shows that a little pressure is constrained to

elbow joint (Argot 2003). In all species except in *M. vinogradovi*, *M. libycus* and *R. opimus*, this status was observed.

355 The broad iliac crests, expanded in the frontal plane (relevant to character 50) may partially related to the width of the trunk and development of the epaxial musculature (Argot 2003; Martin 2005; Kuncová and Frynta 2009). This pattern was observed in *M. tristrami*, *M. vinogradovi*, *M. zarudnyi* and *R. opimus*. On the dorsal margin of the ischium, just posterior to the acetabulum, a rugose tuberosity (character 49) suggests
360 strong pull exerted by the ischio-caudalis (Argot 2003). This status was seen in all species except of *R. norvegicus* and *G. nanus*. The presence of greater trochanter which is extended slightly further medially on the posterior aspect, enclosing a deep trochanteric fossa (character 55) (Rose and Chinnery 2004). This pattern was observed in *T. indica*. In calcaneus, the ovoid cuboid facet (the dorso-ventral diameter slightly greater than the
365 transverse diameter) (character 60) is a plesiomorphic trait (Weisbecker and Schmid 2007; Carrizo et al. 2014) which was only observed in *R. norvegicus*. The deep groove on the ventral aspect of the talus (character 61) helps to dorsiflexion of tibio-talus joint. This groove holds the tibial spine which is a small extension on lateral margin of distal section of tibia (Weisbecker and Schmid 2007).

370 For different species of gerbilline rodents the range of habitat tolerance and preferred habitats for living and nesting are specific or even unique. These could affect the rodent's home range, movement, and activity patterns. For example, fossoriality was strongly related to the greater robusticity in long limb bones of the fore and hindlimb (relevant to several characteristics of limbs, mainly characters 38 and 62) (Seckel and
375 Janis 2008; Samuels and Van Valkenburgh 2008), which was seen in the Great gerbil, *R. opimus*, who lives in sandy or clay deserts, digging very elaborate burrow systems and

adopts a quadrupedal or bipedal alert posture. All members of *R. opimus* sharing a common territory with clear social structure, and releasing alert signals when a predator appears, used to communicate to the group information about a danger (Denys et al. 380 2017).

In saltatorial rodents, feet have elongated metatarsals. Elongation of metatarsals (character 62) and femur bones are significant indicators of cursoriality in many mammals (Weisbecker and Schmid 2007; Seckel and Janis 2008; Samuels and Van Valkenburgh 2008). These were observed in all species except for *R. opimus*. *Tatera indica* occurs in 385 wide variety of habitats, while *M. crassus*, is typically a Saharan species which prefers sandy soils. Similarly, *G. nanus* prefers saline flats and semi-deserts to true sand deserts. *Meriones tristrami* is limited to lowland steppes with enough annual rainfall (more than 100 mm) and soft well-drained soils. In contrast, *M. libycus* prefers compact and hard soils in low-lying areas of arid and semi-arid steppes, deserts, or semi-deserts. The last 390 two species avoid mountain slopes and rocky regions, which are preferred by *M. persicus*, which prefers to shelter on slopes of rocky regions, and never inhabits flat areas. *Meriones vinogradovi* inhabits mountain slopes, semi-desert zones, riverbanks, fallow land and cultivated areas, and does not occur in rocky and sandy areas. Habitat of *M. zarudnyi* is not well known, but probably members of this species live in dry and arid habitats. All 395 above species dig burrows except for *M. persicus*; it uses crevices among rocks or under slabs on slopes as burrows, but also sometimes excavates soil (Denys et al. 2017).

In the case of species which are known to have a large home range and wander far from their burrows especially at night (e.g. *G. nanus* and *M. libycus*), in nomadic mobile species which change their burrows frequently and will move to another site when 400 resources are finished or too poor (e.g. *M. crassus* and *M. libycus*), in solitary species

(e.g. *G. nanus* and *M. libycus*), and/or for species which have dispersed colonies (e.g. *M. persicus*) or living in small groups but not sharing same burrows (e.g. *M. libycus* and *T. indica*) (Denys et al. 2017), elongation of limb bones may equip them with great ability of cursoriality and salutatory to find suitable habitat, foraging and run away from predators. *Meriones vinogradovi* is an exception among the studied *Meriones* species which considered a colonial species with a large number of burrows (Denys et al. 2017). Moreover, there is no information on movement, home range, and social organization of *M. tristrami* and *M. zarudnyi*.

To conclude, functional importance of some morphological variations are still unknown. Some species despite having different size in their skeletal components, have lots of morphological similarities (e.g. *G. nanus* and *T. indica*). Growth rate and growth pattern in bones may have great variations and diversification from one species to another. Furthermore, individuals' variations in skeletal growth due to sexual maturity process are significant. All in all, we remind again that evolution of postcranial skeleton need comprehensive researches in different fields, from molecular and morphological to ecological and developmental studies.

Finally, an identification key for some species of gerbilline rodents in Iran was codified based on morphological characters of postcranial skeleton.

420 **An annotated identification key to the gerbilline rodents**

1: Vertebral column

Centrum shape of C6 in rostral view, transverse foramen of C6 in caudal view, neural spine shape of L3 in dorsal view, status of the angle of two prezygapophyses of sacral

bone in rostral view, presence or absence of connection between neural spines of S1 and
425 S2 of sacral bone in lateral view, respectively:

a) semi-circular, oval, completely robust, open, present.....2a

b) oval, circular, crest-like, close, absent.....2b

2: Manubrium and pectoral girdle

General shape of manubrium in ventral view, general shape of scapula in dorsal view,
430 curvature extent of coracoid process of scapula in lateral view, respectively:

a) long and slender, long and slender, up to the middle of glenoid fossa.....3a

b) not long and slender, not long and slender, straight or up to superior ridge of glenoid
fossa.....3b

3: Pelvic girdle

435 Curvature shape of posterior arc of obturator foramen of innominate bone in lateral view,
shape of pubis tuber in lateral view, shape of the ridge of body of ischium around the
tuberosity of ischium in lateral view, situation of tip of pubis angle in comparison with
anterior arc of obturator foramen in lateral view, respectively:

a) parallel with anterior arc, not picked, arced, in front of $\frac{1}{3}$ inferior of anterior arc.....4a

440 b) not parallel with anterior arc, picked, triangular, in front of the middle superior or lower
than $\frac{1}{2}$ inferior of anterior arc.....4b

4: Hindlimb

Presence or absence of a groove along the lesser trochanter of femur in medial view,
status of calcaneus posterior tuberosity in ventral view, shape of cuboid articular surface
445 in anterior view of calcaneus, respectively:

a) present, developed, oval.....*Rattus norvegicus*

b) absent, explicit, triangular or quadrangular.....5

5: Vertebral column

Status of axial two transverse processes toward each other in ventral view:

- 450 a) create an angle.....6a
b) create an arc or hemiarc.....6b

6: Manubrium and pectoral girdle

Situation of tip of jugular notch angle of manubrium in rostral view, curvature point of acromion process of scapula in dorsal view, respectively:

- 455 a) completely flat, straight.....7a
b) protuberant or picked, to the rostral region.....7b

7: Forelimb

Presence or absence of entepicondylar foramen in epiphysis zone of humerus in caudal view, depression extent of olecranon in caudo-medial view of ulna, respectively:

- 460 a) absent, significant (great).....8a
b) present, not significant (normal or little).....8b

8: Pelvic girdle

Shape of iliopectinal eminence in innominate bone in lateral view:

- a) indeterminate.....9a
465 b) embowed or picked.....9b

9: Posterior limb

Presence or absence of small uncus near the femoral greater trochanter in rostral view, status of femoral trochantric fossa in medial view, shape of femoral greater trochanter in dorsal view, shape of distal metaphysis ridge in caudal view, respectively:

- 470 a) absent, wide, with a deep groove, with eminent ridge.....*Tatera indica*

- b) present, narrow, without groove or with a shallow groove, without ridge or with a short ridge.....10
- 10: Atlantal transverse process extension extent in dorsal view, shape of olecranon superior ridge in caudo-medial view of ulna, respectively:
- 475 a) short and broad, flat and shelvy.....*Gerbillus nanus*
- b) long and extensive, embowed.....11
- 11: Juncture extent of S1- S4 in ventral view of sacral bone, shape of cuboid articular surface in anterior view of calcaneus, respectively:
- a) much or so much, quadrangular.....12
- 480 b) little, oval or triangular.....13b
- 12: Juncture extent of S1- S4 in ventral view of sacral bone:
- a) so much.....13a
- b) much.....17
- 13: Vertebral column
- 485 Shape of the neural spine tip of T2 in dorsal view, intervertebral foramen shape in dorsal view of sacral bone, juncture extent of S1- S4 in ventral view of sacral bone, respectively:
- a) simple, small, so much.....14a
- b) pitchfork, big, much.....14b
- 14: Manubrium and pectoral girdle
- 490 Shape of manubrium ventral crest in ventral view, presence or absence of an accessory uncus near the first rib tubercle in rostral view, status of superior process of scapula spine in dorsal view, respectively:
- a) gross and robust, present, completely significant and prominent.....15a
- b) normal, absent, a little significant15b

495	15: Limbs	
	Shape of ulnar tuberosity in caudo-medial view of ulna, depression extent of olecranon in caudo-medial view of ulna, shape of 3 rd metatarsal in lateral view, respectively:	
	a) gross and robust, a little, short and robust.....	<i>Rhombomys opimus</i>
	b) linear and crest-like, normal, normal.....	16
500	16: Caudal extension extent of axial neural process in lateral view, general shape of scapula in dorsal view, respectively:	
	a) much, broad and short.....	<i>Meriones vinogradovi</i>
	b) little, normal.....	17
	17: Status of neural spine in rostral view of Ca4:	
505	a) completely eroded.....	18
	b) with partly or completely growth	19
	18: Presence or absence of a small fossa on the olecranon in caudo-medial view of ulna:	
	a) present.....	<i>Meriones zarudnyi</i>
	b) absent.....	<i>Meriones persicus</i>
510	19: Shape of semilunar notch in rostro-lateral view of ulna:	
	a) triangular.....	20
	b) semicircular.....	<i>Meriones tristrami</i>
	20: Depression extent of proximal part of manubrium in apical region in rostral view, status of Ca4 neural spine in rostral view, status of Ca4 transverse process in rostral view, respectively:	
515	a) wholly flat, completely grown, completely divergent.....	<i>Meriones crassus</i>
	b) with depression, partly eroded, partly divergent.....	<i>Meriones libycus</i>

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Table legends:

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Table 1. Collecting sites for rodents used in the present study. Numbers of captured rodents from each locality or museum specimens are indicated in parentheses. Numbers of the studied mature male specimens are shown.

Species	Total specimen	Collecting site/ Museum collection	Studied mature male specimen
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	11	Mashhad (11)	8
<i>Gerbillus nanus</i>	5	ZMFUM ¹ (5)	5
<i>Tatera indica</i>	7	Khaf (5), Torbat-e Heydarieh (2)	7
<i>Rhombomys opimus</i>	9	Bojnord (1), ZMFUM ¹ (8)	7
<i>Meriones crassus</i>	9	Khaf (3), Torbat-e Heydarieh (6)	7
<i>Meriones libycus</i>	15	Sarakhs (3), Chenaran (2), Shirvan (7), Qaen (2), Nehbandan (1)	11

		Farooj (2), Fariman (5),	
<i>Meriones persicus</i>	18	Mashhad (5), Kalat (4), Dargaz (1), Birjand (1)	12
<i>Meriones tristrami</i>	4	Zanjan (1), ZMFUM ¹ (3)	3
<i>Meriones vinogradovi</i>	3	Zanjan (1), ZMFUM ¹ (2)	3
<i>Meriones zarudnyi</i>	1	Shirvan (1)	1
Total	82		64

¹ ZMFUM: Zoological Museum, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad

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Table 2. List of character states and character treatment (polarity) of postcranial skeleton in the present study.

Vertebral column

Atlas (dorsal view)

- 710 1. Atlantal transverse process extension extent in dorsal view: short and broad (0); long and extensive (1), following Argot (2003) and Carrizo et al. (2014) with modification.

Axis (ventral view)

- 715 2. Status of axial two transverse processes toward each other in ventral view: create an arc (0); create a hemi-arc (1); create an angle (2).

Axis (lateral view)

3. Caudal extension extent of axial neural process in lateral view: great extension (0); little extension (1), following Steppan (1995), Argot (2003), and Carrizo et al. (2014) with modification.

720 *Sixth cervical vertebra (rostral view)*

4. Form of the situation angle of carotid tubercle toward the centrum: vertical (0); wide (1).
5. Centrum shape of C6 in rostral view: oval (0); semi-circular (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

725 *Sixth cervical vertebra (caudal view)*

6. Transverse foramen of C6 in caudal view: circular (0); oval (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Second thoracic vertebra (dorsal view)

7. Shape of the neural spine tip of T2 in dorsal view: pitchfork (0); simple (1),
730 following Carleton (1980) and Stepan (1995) with modification.

Thoracic and lumbar vertebra

8. Total number of thoracic and lumbar vertebra: thirteen (0); twelve (1),
following Carleton (1980), Stepan (1995) and Pacheco (2003).

Third lumbar vertebra (dorsal view)

735 9. Neural spine shape of L3 in dorsal view: crest-like (0); completely robust (1),
following Argot (2003), Martin (2005), Kuncová and Frynta (2009), and
Carrizo et al. (2014) with modification.

Sacral vertebra (lateral view)

10. Connection between neural spines of S1 and S2 of sacral bone in lateral view:
740 absent (0); present (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

11. Shape of anterior zygapophysis: lunate (0); with conic tip (1), based on
illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

12. Degree of sacral curvature: little (0); great (1).

Sacral vertebra (rostral view)

745 13. Status of the angle of two prezygapophyses of sacral bone in rostral view: close
(0); open (1).

Sacral vertebra (ventral view)

14. Juncture extent of S1-S4 in ventral view of sacral bone: little, vertebral disc is
visible (0); much, vertebral disc going to disappear (1); so much, with
750 disappeared vertebral disc (2), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Sacral vertebra (dorsal view)

15. Intervertebral foramen shape in dorsal view of sacral bone: big (0); small (1).

16. Connection between S4 with other sacral vertebra: present (0); absent (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

755 ***Fourth caudal vertebra (dorsal view)***

17. Shape of the transverse processes: robust and short (0); long (1), following Argot (2003) and Carrizo et al. (2014) with modification.

18. A foramen on the transverse processes: absent (0); present (1), following Argot (2003) with modification and also based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

760 ***Fourth caudal vertebra (rostral view)***

19. Status of neural spine in rostral view of Ca4: completely erosion (0); moderate; with partly growth (1); completely growth (2).

20. Status of Ca4 transverse process in rostral view: partly divergent (0); completely divergent (1).

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External anatomy

General form of tail

21. Location of the longest caudal vertebra: in the middle of the tail length (0); in the first 1/3 proximal of tail length (1), following Stepan (1995) with modification.

770

22. Tail length compared with the head and body length: longer (0); equal (1); shorter (2), following Stepan (1995) with modification.

Manubrium and pectoral girdle

775 ***Manubrium (ventral view)***

23. General shape of manubrium in ventral view: short and broad (0); moderate (1); long and slender (2), following Sa´nchez-Villagra et al. (2006) with modification.

24. Shape of manubrium ventral crest in ventral view: thin (0); moderate (1); gross and robust (2), following Argot (2003) and Martin (2005) with modification.

780 ***Manubrium (rostral view)***

25. Situation of tip of jugular notch angle of manubrium in rostral view: completely flat (0); protuberant (1); picked (2).

26. Depression extent of proximal part of manubrium in apical region in rostral view: wholly flat (0); with depression (1).

785 ***First rib (caudal view)***

27. Shape of the rib angle: arc (0); nearly straight (1).

First rib (rostral view)

28. Presence or absence of an accessory uncus near the first rib tubercle in rostral view: absent (0); present (1), following Carleton (1980) with modification.

790 ***Clavicle (ventral view)***

29. Position of the costo-clavicular ligament at the sternal end: not distinguishable (0); distinguishable (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Scapula (dorsal view)

795 30. Status of superior process of scapula spine in dorsal view: little significant (0); significant (1); completely significant and prominent (2), following Martin (2005), Seckel and Janis (2008), and Morgan (2009) with modification.

31. General shape of scapula in dorsal view: short and broad (0); moderate (1); long and slender (2), following Argot (2003), Martin (2005), Seckel and Janis (2008), and Kuncová and Frynta (2009) with modification.

800 32. Curvature point of acromion process of scapula in dorsal view: to the rostral
region (0); straight (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Scapula (lateral view)

33. Curvature extent of coracoid process of scapula in lateral view: straight (0); up to
the superior ridge of glenoid fossa (1); up to the middle of glenoid fossa (2),
805 following Carleton (1980) and Sa´nchez-Villagra et al. (2006) with modification.

Forelimb

Humerus (caudal view)

34. Entepicondylar foramen in epiphysis zone of humerus in caudal view: present
810 (0); absent (1), following Carleton (1980), Stepan (1995) and Pacheco (2003).

35. Depth of the groove associated with ulnar nerve: little (0); great (1), following
Argot (2003) and Sa´nchez-Villagra et al. (2006) with modification.

Humerus (medial view)

36. Status of deltoid tuberosity toward the body of humerus: form a lunate (0);
815 form a hook (1), following Stepan (1995) and Sa´nchez-Villagra et al. (2006)
with modification.

Ulna (caudo-medial view)

37. Shape of olecranon superior ridge in caudo-medial view of ulna: embowed (0);
flat and shelvy (1), following Rose and Chinnery (2004) with modification.

820 38. Shape of ulnar tuberosity in caudo-medial view of ulna: linear and crest-like
(0); gross and robust (1), following Samuels and Van Valkenburgh (2008) and
Seckel and Janis (2008) with modification.

39. Depression extent of olecranon in caudo-medial view of ulna: significant (great) (0); moderate (1); little (2), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

825 40. A small fossa on the olecranon in caudo-medial view of ulna: absent (0); present (1).

Ulna (rostro-lateral view)

41. Shape of semilunar notch in rostro-lateral view of ulna: semi-circular (0); triangular (1).

830 42. A sharp tubercle on the medial edge of the ulnar body (shaft): present (0); absent (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Ulna (caudo-medial view)

43. Convex degree of the radius shaft in lateral (external) part: little (0); great (1).

835 **Pelvic girdle**

Innominate bone (lateral view)

840 44. Curvature shape of posterior arc of obturator foramen of innominate bone in lateral view: with a triangular-like posterior curvature (0); with a semi-circular-like posterior curvature (1); parallel with anterior arc (2), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

45. Shape of pubis tuber in lateral view: picked (0); not picked, arced (1).

46. Shape of the ridge of body of ischium around the tuberosity of ischium in lateral view: triangular (0); arced (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

845 47. Situation of tip of pubis angle in comparison with anterior arc of obturator foramen in lateral view: in front of the middle superior of anterior arc (0); lower than 1/2 inferior of anterior arc (1); in front of 1/3 inferior of anterior arc (2).

48. Length of pubis symphysis as compared with the distance between the tip of pubis angle and iliopectinal eminence: longer (0); shorter (1).

850 49. Amount of protuberance of the tuberosity of ischium: great (0); little (1), following Argot (2003) with modification.

50. Shape of iliopectinal eminence in innominate bone in lateral view: embowed (0); picked (1); indeterminate (2), following Argot (2003), Martin (2005), and Kuncová and Frynta (2009) with modification.

855 **Hindlimb**

Femur (rostral view)

51. Small uncus near the femoral greater trochanter in rostral view: present (0); absent (1).

860 52. Status of anterior intertrochanteric crest: indeterminate (0); moderate (1); completely determinate (2), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

53. Position of lesser trochanter toward the femur body: create a lunate (0); create an angle (1).

Femur (medial view)

865 54. A groove along the lesser trochanter of femur in medial view: absent (0); present (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

55. Status of femoral trochantric fossa in medial view: narrow (0); deep and wide (1), following Rose and Chinnery (2004) with modification.

Femur (caudal view)

870 56. Shape of distal metaphysis ridge in caudal view: without ridge (0); with a short ridge (1); with an eminent ridge (2), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Femur (dorsal view)

57. Shape of femoral greater trochanter in dorsal view: without groove (0); with a shallow groove (1); with a deep groove (2).

Calcaneus (ventral view)

875 58. Status of calcaneus posterior tuberosity in ventral view: explicit (0); developed (1), following Carleton (1980) and Sa´nchez-Villagra et al. (2006) with modification.

Calcaneus (medial view)

880 59. Status of the groove for the tendon of flexor hallucis longus muscle: deep (0); shallow (1), based on illustrations of Bab et al. (2007).

Calcaneus (anterior view)

60. Shape of cuboid articular surface in anterior view of calcaneus: oval (0); triangular (1); quadrangular (2), following Sa´nchez-Villagra (2006), Weisbecker and Schmid (2007), and Carrizo et al. (2014) with modification.

885 ***Talus (ventral view)***

61. Status of talus groove: deep (0); shallow (1), following Weisbecker and Schmid (2007) with modification.

Third metatarsal (lateral view)

890 62. Shape of third metatarsal in lateral view: normal (0); short and robust (1), following Pacheco (2003) and Sa´nchez-Villagra (2006) with modification.

895 **Table 3.** Taxon-multistate characters matrix used for the cladistic analyses. The number of characters is the same as Table 2.

Species	Character No.
	123456789111111111122222222223333333333344444444445555555555666 012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012
Rattus norvegicus	00011100110010010010022011100120210010100002112110100100011010
Tatera indica	02010001000100010010001101000011011010000001000102100012200100
Gerbillus nanus	000000000000000010010101021001010100010100000001110000000100100
Meriones crassus	101000000000000001021021020100110100000101100000000000001000100
Meriones libycus	1010000000010000000100210210001101000001010010000001010001000100
Meriones persicus	10110001001000000000101121000110100000100110000001010000000110
Meriones tristrami	10100001001000001010011121001110100100100100000001000000000100
Meriones vinogradovi	100000000000010001101211100100010000010000000000021001001200
Meriones zarudnyi	11100001001000001100110121001110001100110110000000021001000100
Rhombomys opimus	10000011001102101010120211010210101001200010001100020000000201

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915 **Figure legends:**

Fig. 1. Sampling localities. North Khorasan province: Farooj, Shirvan, and Bojnord; Razavi Khorasan province: Mashhad, Kalat, Dargaz, Chenaran, Sarakhs, Khaf, Torbat-e Heydarieh, and Fariman; South Khorasan: Qaen, Birjand, and Nehbandan;

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and Zanzan province: Zanzan. Gerbilline rodents were captured using custom-made mesh live traps and Faragir traps.

Fig. 2. Representative of informative characters of vertebral column (part I) in gerbilline

species. **(A)** Atlas (D.): the extension extent of atlantad transverse processes with
 925 two character states; short and broad (RNO, GNA, TIN) or long and extensive (all
 others). **(B)** Axis (V.): status of two transverse processes toward each other with
 two character states; create an angle (TIN) or an arc (all others). **(C)** Axis (Lt.): the
 extension extent of neural process with two character states; great (RNO, GNA,
 TIN, ROP, MVI) or little (all others). **(D)** C6 (R.): shape of centrum with two
 930 character states; semi-circular (RNO) oval or (all others). **(E)** C6 (CA.): shape of
 transverse foramen with two character states; oval (RNO) or circular (all others).
(F) T2 (D.): shape of the tip of the neural spine with two character states; simple

(ROP) or pitchfork (all others). (G) L3 (D.): shape of neural spine with two character states; completely robust (RNO) or crest- like (all others). Abbreviations
935 are described in the text. Characters and character states correspond Table 2.

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Fig. 3. Representative of informative characters of vertebral column (part II) in gerbilline

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species. **(A)** Sacrum (Lt.): presence of a connection between the neural spines of S1

and S2 with two character states; present (RNO) or absent (all others). **(B)** Sacrum

(R.): status of the angle of two prezygapophyses with two character states; open

(RNO) or close (all others). **(C)** Sacrum (V.): junction extent of S1-S4 with three

character states; great (ROP), intermediate (MVI) or little (all others). **(D)** Sacrum

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(D.): a junction between S4 and other sacral vertebra with two character states;

absent (RNO, GNA, TIN) or present (all others). Shape of intervertebral foramen

with two character states; small (ROP) or big (all others). **(E)** Ca4 (R.): status of

neural spine with three character states; partially grown (RNO, GNA, TIN, ROP,
MLI, MPE, MVI), completely grown (MCR), or completely eroded (MTR,
955 MZA). Status of transverse processes with two character states; completely
divergent (MCR) or partially divergent (all others). Abbreviations are described in
the text. Characters and character states correspond Table 2.

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965 **Fig. 4.** Representative of informative characters of thorax, and pectoral and pelvic girdles
 in gerbilline species. **(A)** Manubrium (V.): shape of the manubrium with three
 character states; slender (RNO), short and broad (ROP, MZA) or long (all others).
 Shape of manubrium ventral crest with three character states; fine (RNO, GNA,
 MCR, MLI), robust (ROP) or normal (all others). **(B)** Manubrium (R.): situation of
 970 tip of the jugular notch angle with three character states; completely flat (TIN),
 protuberant (RNO, ROP, MVI) or picked (all others). Depression extent of
 proximal part of the manubrium in apical region with two character states; wholly
 flat (MCR) or with depression (all others). **(C)** First rib (R.): an accessory uncus
 near the tubercle of first rib with two character states; present (ROP) or absent (all

975 others). **(D)** Scapula (D.): general shape of scapula with three character states; long
and slender (RNO), short and broad (ROP, MVI), or intermediate (all others).
Curvature point of the acromion process with two character states; straight (TIN)
or with the curvature to the rostral region (all others). Status of superior process of
scapula spine with three character states; not significant (TIN, MVI), completely
980 prominent (ROP), significant (all others). **(E)** Scapula (Lt.): curvature extent of
coracoid process with three character states; long, up to the middle of glenoid fossa
(RNO), straight (TIN, MZA), or short and up to the superior ridge of glenoid fossa
(all others). **(F)** Innominate bone (Lt.): shape of posterior arc of obturator foramen
with three character states; parallel with anterior arc (RNO), with semi-circular
985 posterior curvature (TIN, MLI) or with triangular posterior curvature (all others).
Shape of pubic tuber with two character states; not picked (RNO) or picked (all
others). Shape of the ridge of ischium body around the tuberosity of the ischium
with two character states; arched (RNO) or triangular (all others). Situation of the
tip of pubic angle in related to the anterior arc of the obturator foramen with three
990 character states; in front of the $\frac{1}{3}$ inferior of the anterior arc (RNO), lower than
 $\frac{1}{2}$ inferior of the anterior arc (GNA, ROP) or in front of the $\frac{1}{2}$ superior of the
anterior arc (all others). Shape of iliopectinal eminence with three character states;
indeterminate (TIN), picked (MLI, MPE, MTR) or embowed (all others).
Abbreviations are described in the text. Characters and character states correspond
995 Table 2.

Fig. 5. Representative of informative characters of fore- and hindlimbs in gerbilline species. (A) Humerus (CA.): an entepicondylar foramen in epiphysis zone with two character states; absent (RNO, TIN) or present (all others). (B) Ulna (C.M.): depression extent of olecranon with three character states; significant (great) (TIN), not significant (little) (ROP), or intermediate (all others). Shape of olecranon superior ridge with two character states; flat and shelvy (RNO, GNA, TIN) or embowed (all others). Shape of the ulnar tuberosity with two character states; gross and robust (ROP) or linear and crest-like (all others). A small fossa on the olecranon with two character states; present (MZA) or absent (all others). (C) Ulna (R.L.): shape of semilunar notch with two character states; triangular (MCR, MLI) or semi-circular (all others). (D) Femur (R.): a small uncus near the greater trochanter with two character states; absent (RNO, TIN) or present (all others). (E) Femur (M.): a

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groove along the lesser trochanter with two character states; present (RNO) or
1010 absent (all others). Status of trochantric fossa with two character states; wide (TIN)
or narrow (all others). **(F)** Femur (CA.): shape of the distal metaphysis ridge with
two character states; with eminent ridge (TIN) or without ridge (all others). **(G)**
Femur (D.): shape of greater trochanter of femur with three character states; with a
shallow groove (GNA), with a deep groove (TIN) or without groove (all others).
1015 **(H)** Calcaneus (V.): status of posterior tuberosity with two character states;
developed (RNO) or explicit (all others). **(I)** Calcaneus (Ant.): shape of the cuboid
articular surface with three character states; oval (RNO), quadrangular (ROP, MVI)
or triangular (all others). **(J)** Third metatarsal (Lt.): shape of third metatarsal with
two character states; short and robust (ROP) or normal (all others). Abbreviations
1020 are described in the text. Characters and character states correspond Table 2.

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Fig. 6. Strict consensus tree based on Camin-Sokal parsimony constructed with CONSENSE (majority-rule and strict consensus tree program v. 3.573c), and then drawn with TreeView v. 1.6.1. Numbers above the lines, near each nodes, are bootstrap values.